

Investigating the Relationship between Communication Skills and Marital Satisfaction: The Mediating Role of Perfectionism

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Abstract

Background and Purpose: The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between communication skills with marital satisfaction with considering the mediating role of perfectionism.

Methods: The current study utilized a descriptive-correlation approach, employing structural equation modeling. The research focused on married individuals residing in Tehran, with a marriage duration of less than 25 years. A sample of 200 participants (100 couples) was chosen from this population using an available sampling method. Standard questionnaires were used for data collection. Pearson correlation test and the structural equation modeling were used for data analysis.

Results: Results revealed that communication skills significantly affected marital satisfaction ($T=6.284$). Moreover, communication skills significantly affected perfectionism ($T=11.594$). Furthermore, perfectionism significantly affected marital satisfaction ($T=9.509$). Finally, perfectionism has significantly mediated the relationship between communication skills and marital satisfaction ($P<0.001$). Results of model fit indicated that the research model has good fit.

Conclusion: According to the results of this study, it is advised that couples concentrate on fostering and improving the aspects that support communication skills. Furthermore, more attention should be given to perfectionism.

Keywords: Communication skills, marital satisfaction, perfectionism, marriage, mediation

Introduction

Marriage is an essential aspect of human nature, present in all living beings (Fowers & Olson, 1993). It is considered a pathway towards achieving perfection, yet in today's society, it has become a complex phenomenon (Hou, et al. 2019). Marital satisfaction plays a crucial role in enhancing psychological well-being and family harmony. Therefore, it is imperative to recognize the factors that contribute to satisfaction in marital relationships (Lee & McKinnish, 2019). Marital satisfaction refers to the psychological state where an individual is content and happy with the advantages and drawbacks of their marriage with their partner. It is a personal evaluation based on one's needs, expectations, and desires within the relationship (Tahan, et al. 2020). Marital satisfaction is a relatively consistent attitude that mirrors an individual's overall assessment of the partnership. It is not a feature of the relationship itself, but rather a subjective viewpoint and personal experience (Abdi, et al. 2022; Whisman, et al. 2018).

A strong marital relationship is crucial for the well-being of spouses, children, and other family members, as well as for society as a whole. Healthy couples contribute to the creation of healthy families, which in turn play a significant role in shaping a healthy society (Bradbury, et al. 2000). Therefore, prioritizing the health of the family, as the primary social unit, is essential for the overall well-being of communities (Afsanepurak, et al. 2012; Charnia & Ickes, 2007; Bir Aktürk, 2006; Dakin & Wampler, 2008). Marital satisfaction is a key factor in

determining family health, as it directly impacts the mental well-being of the family unit. It can be seen as a foundational element of the family system, providing vital support and rejuvenation for the family structure (Idemudia & Ndlovu, 2013; Bradbury, et al. 2000; Campbell, 2009; Guttman & Lazar, 2004).

Marital satisfaction can be impacted by a multitude of factors, including cognition, physiology, interaction patterns, spouse and marital characteristics, life events, and spiritual commitment (Bradbury, et al. 2000; Dana & Shams, 2019; Edwards, 2009; Guo & Huang, 2005; Meyers & Landsberger, 2002). The level of satisfaction experienced within a marriage holds great importance, as it can greatly affect the overall well-being and health of both spouses, as well as their children and families (Dana, et al. 2021; Epstein, et al. 2005; Dethier, et al. 2011; Ghorbani et al. 2020). Furthermore, it is worth noting that marital satisfaction is not a static concept, but rather, it can evolve and fluctuate over time, influenced by the stage and duration of the marriage (Bartee, 2011; Greeff & Malherbe, 2001).

Marriage relies heavily on the quality of the relationship between spouses, and effective communication skills serve as a crucial indicator of satisfaction within this relationship (De-Beer, 2017). Through the use of communication skills, individuals can engage in interpersonal interactions and navigate the communication process using various techniques such as verbal skills, active listening, and providing feedback (Firat & Okanlı, 2019; Ghorbani & Bund, 2014, 2016, 2017). Extensive research has consistently highlighted communication problems as one of the most prevalent issues expressed by couples, with over 87% of troubled couples identifying these problems as the primary source of their relationship difficulties (Haris & Kumar, 2018). Establishing effective communication within a marital relationship fosters a strong and intimate bond, enabling spouses to meet each other's needs, support one another, spend quality time together, and maintain emotional closeness. The notion that communication skills significantly influence marital satisfaction has been extensively explored in couple therapy theories and numerous studies (Lavner, et al. 2016; Rehman, et al. 2011; Sadeghipor & Aghdam, 2021). Research has consistently demonstrated a positive and significant correlation between communication skills and marital satisfaction. However, in today's digital age, the widespread availability, and accessibility of the Internet and virtual social networks have introduced a new form of interpersonal communication (Litzinger & Gordon, 2007; Dagari & Adamu, 2019; Sadeghipor, et al. 2021). This phenomenon has become an integral part of people's daily lives, necessitating an examination of its impact on couples' relationships and their overall satisfaction (Burlison & Denton, 1997; Crash, et al. 1989; Sadeghipor, et al. 2021). Hence, the first aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between communication skills with marital satisfaction.

In addition, perfectionism undoubtedly plays a significant role in the compatibility of individuals and in the development, persistence, and clinical course of psychopathology (Buhrman, et al. 2020; Swami & Mammadova, 2012; Egan, 2013; Moradi et al. 2020; Sadeghpour & Sangchini, 2020). Throughout history, psychologists have shown great interest in the concept of perfectionism, as it often involves the imposition of unrealistic standards by others, making it exceedingly challenging to meet these expectations (Palha -Fernandes, et al. 2019; Seyedi Asl et al, 2016, 2021). Given that these standards are extreme and externally imposed, they can lead to a sense of helplessness and a lack of control, resulting in feelings of failure, anxiety, anger, and despair. While there is no universally accepted definition of "perfectionism," it is widely regarded as a personality trait associated with success and personal growth, characterized by an intense and obsessive pursuit of high standards and excessive self-expectations (Ong, et al. 2021; Stoeber & Stoeber, 2009; Taghva et al. 2020). While many researchers view perfectionism as a debilitating trait, others argue that it can serve as a beneficial motivational factor, driving individuals towards success and the attainment of excellence and perfection (Hewitt, 2009; Smith, et al. 2019; Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Consequently, it can be inferred that perfectionism influences the relationship between communication skills and marital satisfaction. Hence, in this study, it was aimed to investigate the mediating role of perfectionism in the relationship between communication skills with marital satisfaction. Overall, the aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between communication skills with marital satisfaction with considering the mediating role of perfectionism.

Methods

The current study utilized a descriptive-correlation approach, employing structural equation modeling. The research focused on married individuals residing in Tehran, with a marriage duration of less than 25 years. A sample of 200 participants (100 couples) was chosen from this population using an available sampling method. The inclusion criteria involved having no more than 3 children and no history of divorce or remarriage for either spouse. Trained moderators, consisting of five men and five women, assisted in selecting the sample and administering the questionnaires. They visited the participants' homes, obtained informed consent from both partners, provided the necessary tools for data collection, and instructed them to complete the questionnaires separately. Participants were also instructed to assign a unique code to maintain confidentiality. Additionally, participants were given the option to contact a designated phone number to inquire about their questionnaire

results. These procedures effectively motivated couples to complete the questionnaires individually and stay engaged with the study results.

In this research, the following tools were used to collect data:

The ENRICH Marital Satisfaction Questionnaire was developed by Olson in 1994 to assess the level of marital satisfaction (Charnia & Ickes, 2007; Bir Aktürk, 2006). According to Olson, this questionnaire is able to identify the key aspects of a marital relationship, including its strengths, potential issues, and can also serve as a diagnostic tool for couples seeking counseling to improve their relationship. This questionnaire has been widely utilized in research due to its reliability. Olson and his colleagues have reported a validity coefficient of 0.92 using the alpha coefficient method. However, the original version of the questionnaire, consisting of 115 questions, can be tiring for respondents. However, the short form has been found to have an internal correlation of 0.95. In this particular research, a 47-question form was used, with response options ranging from "I completely disagree" to "I completely agree," scored from 1 to 5. The total score range was between 47 and 235, with higher scores indicating greater marital satisfaction. The present study found an internal consistency of 0.96 for the questionnaire using Cronbach's alpha method.

The Marital Communication Skills Questionnaire was developed by Moradi in 2000 (Firat & Okanlı, 2019). Moradi's research focused on the impact of teaching communication skills on marital compatibility. This questionnaire consists of 36 questions with five choices each: never, rarely, sometimes, most of the time, and always, graded from 0 to 4. Scores on the questionnaire range from 0 to 144, with higher scores indicating better communication skills. The internal consistency of the questionnaire in the current study was found to be 0.89.

The Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale (MPS) was utilized to assess perfectionism (Buhrman, et al. 2020; Swami & Mammadova, 2012). This scale consists of 35 items based on a five-point scale ranging from completely agree (score 5) to completely disagree (score 1). Scores on the questionnaire range from 35 to 175, with higher scores indicating higher perfectionism. In the current study, Cronbach's alpha coefficients was 0.83.

We utilized SPSS-26 and Lisrel software to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were employed to characterize the variables. Pearson correlation test was conducted to assess the relationships between the variables. The structural equation method was applied to investigate the relationship between communication skills with martial satisfaction with considering the mediating role of perfectionism. One-way analysis of variance and LSD follow-up test were used for comparing the research variables among the participants with different martial age categories. The significance level was set at $P < 0.05$.

Results

The mean age for women was 31.65 years with a standard deviation of 7.32, while husbands had an average age of 36.97 years with a standard deviation of 6.71. Among women, 56.75% were housewives and 43.25% were employed. For men, 25% were employees and 75% were self-employed.

To compare the participants based on the variables under study, the duration of marriage was categorized into three groups: 1-8 years, 9-16 years, and more than 16 years. The results of the one-way analysis of variance and LSD follow-up test indicated that there was no significant difference in terms of marital satisfaction ($F = 0.920, p = 0.381$) and communication skills ($F = 0.163, p = 0.850$) among the different groups. However, there was a statistically significant difference among different categories regarding perfectionism ($F = 5.694, p < 0.001$). Individuals in the first 8 years of marriage had higher scores in terms of perfectionism.

The results of the one-way variance analysis revealed significant differences in marital satisfaction ($F = 3.799, p = 0.006$), communication skills ($F = 5.175, p = 0.001$) and perfectionism ($F = 6.917, p < 0.001$) among the participants with different educational levels. Further analysis using LSD follow-up tests indicated that individuals with master's degrees exhibited higher marital satisfaction, communication skills and perfectionism compared to those with bachelor's degrees, diplomas, and lower.

Moreover, descriptive results (Table 1) show that in general the level of communication skills is lower than the average. However, martial satisfaction and perfectionism were at medium level. The results of Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests revealed that all variables were normally distributed (all $P > 0.05$). Results of Independent t tests showed that there were no significant differences between men and women in all variables of the study.

Table 1. Descriptive Data

	Martial Satisfaction	Communication Skills	Perfectionism
Mean	101.64	74.33	89.54
SD	25.78	9.49	8.47

Bivariate relationships between communication skills with martial satisfaction and perfectionism are demonstrated in Table 2. Results revealed significant direct relationship between communication skills and martial satisfaction ($P < 0.001$). Moreover, communication skills were directly and significantly associated with

perfectionism ($P < 0.001$). Finally, perfectionism was directly and significantly associated with marital satisfaction ($P < 0.001$).

Table 2. Results of Bivariate Relationships between Variables

	1	2	3
1. Communication Skills	-		
2. Marital Satisfaction	$r=0.625$ $P < 0.001$	-	
3. Perfectionism	$r=0.409$ $P < 0.001$	$r=0.543$ $P < 0.001$	-

Table 3 and Figure 1 show the results of structural equation modelling. Results revealed that communication skills significantly affected marital satisfaction ($T=6.284$). Moreover, communication skills significantly affected perfectionism ($T=11.594$). Furthermore, perfectionism significantly affected marital satisfaction ($T=9.509$). Finally, perfectionism has significantly mediated the relationship between communication skills and marital satisfaction ($P < 0.001$). Results of model fit are presented in Table 4 and indicated that the research model has good fit.

Table 3. Results of Structural Equation Modelling

Path	β	T-value
1 Communication Skills => marital satisfaction	0.681	7.025
2 Communication Skills => perfectionism	0.397	4.684
3 Perfectionism => marital satisfaction	0.550	5.967
	Z	P-value
4 Communication Skills => perfectionism => marital satisfaction	4.870	$P < 0.001$

Figure 1. Structural Equation Modelling in the form of T-Values

Table 4. Results of Model Fit

Index	Optimal Range	Obtained Value	Conclusion
RMSEA	< 0.08	0.06	Good fit
X^2 / df	< 3	2.83	Good fit
RMR	Closer to 0	0.02	Good fit
NFI	> 0.9	0.95	Good fit
CFI	> 0.9	0.97	Good fit

Discussion

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between communication skills with marital satisfaction with considering the mediating role of perfectionism. The findings of this study showed that communication skills affect positively marital satisfaction. This finding is in line with those of previous studies (Firat & Okanlı, 2019; Ghorbani & Bund, 2014, 2016, 2017). Researchers have indicated that couples who are seemingly unhappy may suffer from a lack of skills that hinder effective communication. This deficiency significantly contributes to marital dissatisfaction. Additionally, couples who lack the necessary skills to regulate emotional expression and establish successful communication tend to become defensive or avoid conflict situations (De-Beer, 2017). These behaviors, in turn, lead to dissatisfaction and the breakdown of the marriage. The acquisition of communication skills is crucial in creating and maintaining intimacy, as most tensions arise

from ineffective communication (Haris & Kumar, 2018). By acknowledging and developing effective ways of communicating with each other, many problems can be identified and managed. Good communication skills are among the most important factors for satisfaction in marital relationships, and the level of satisfaction in a relationship depends on effective communication (Lavner, et al. 2016; Rehman, et al. 2011; Sadeghipor & Aghdam, 2021). Individuals who struggle to communicate face consequences such as life dissatisfaction, premature mortality, a lack of identity, and poor relationship development. On the other hand, possessing communication skills leads to improved relationships, better handling of challenging situations, enhanced mental and physical health, and improved social performance. Therefore, the quality of communication plays a vital role in marital satisfaction, with communication skills serving as the primary factor in couples' satisfaction.

Moreover, the results of this study showed that communication skills were directly and significantly associated with perfectionism. Perfectionism refers to the conscious methods and strategies employed by individuals to address problems. The ultimate goal of these methods is to either solve the problem at hand or enhance the individual's psychological resilience, enabling them to effectively navigate critical situations and avoid mental crises (Buhrman, et al. 2020; Swami & Mammadova, 2012; Egan, 2013; Moradi et al. 2020; Sadeghpour & Sangchini, 2020). On the other hand, ineffective factors are those efforts that, despite being utilized to tackle difficult situations, often exacerbate the problem and complicate the situation further. Coping mechanisms enable individuals to utilize their skills and demonstrate their ability to manage life's challenges and problems. This definition emphasizes the process-oriented nature of coping, rather than focusing on inherent traits (Palha -Fernandes, et al. 2019; Seyedi Asl et al, 2016, 2021). It suggests that people respond to perfectionism based on various factors such as timing, past experiences, and the nature of the event, rather than relying solely on predetermined plans and designs. Consequently, this definition does not evaluate coping based on outcomes and success. In other words, it assists individuals in overcoming their problems, but it does not necessarily guarantee problem resolution. Another noteworthy aspect of this definition is the recognition of the unique interplay between personality and environmental factors when confronted with perfectionism-related events (Ong, et al. 2021; Stoeber & Stoeber, 2009; Taghva et al. 2020). Therefore, skills are acquired through the interaction between individuals and their environment, specifically through the individual's assessment of the situation, available resources, and the adoption of adaptive coping behaviors.

Finally, the results of this study showed that perfectionism has significantly mediated the relationship between communication skills and marital satisfaction. In explaining this discovery, one can argue that perfectionism necessitates inappropriate levels of expectations and concrete objectives, as well as a perpetual sense of dissatisfaction, regardless of one's performance. Order and organization are integral components of self-centered perfectionism, wherein an individual demands perfection from themselves. This mindset establishes unattainable benchmarks and fixates on flaws and failures in performance (Dana, et al. 2021; Epstein, et al. 2005; Dethier, et al. 2011; Ghorbani et al. 2020). Additionally, it fixates on the fear of making mistakes. These factors serve as the foundation for anxiety and stress. Consequently, an individual who fixates on their weaknesses and is engrossed in intellectual work within this domain will encounter dysfunction in other aspects of their life. This circumstance also impacts an individual's intimate relationship with their spouse and may even give rise to unreasonable expectations (such as expecting one's partner to also be flawless). In this scenario, the individual suffers from other-oriented perfectionism, wherein they believe that others must be perfect. Consequently, they consistently blame their partner for not conforming to their standards. This matter is not acceptable to everyone, and consequently, these extreme personal standards contribute to an increase in negative experiences. By magnifying these experiences, individuals begin to feel frustrated and depressed, thus entering into a harmful cycle (Palha -Fernandes, et al. 2019; Seyedi Asl et al, 2016, 2021). This cycle entails a depressed mood that leads to a heightened focus on personal and others' shortcomings. Furthermore, the absence of any change in circumstances only deepens the feeling of disappointment. All of these factors significantly diminish the quality of one's marital life and result in a lack of satisfaction within the relationship. Moreover, perfectionists tend to have unrealistic expectations of their marital bond, which ultimately damages their self-esteem. This decrease in self-esteem then impacts various aspects of their life. Perfectionists struggle to adopt a problem-oriented coping style when faced with difficulties, instead resorting to an emotional coping style that negatively affects their marriage (Ong, et al. 2021; Stoeber & Stoeber, 2009; Taghva et al. 2020). Some perfectionists even procrastinate due to their fear of not being able to complete tasks in the best possible manner. Consequently, they experience low self-confidence and become stressed, which inevitably spills over into their marital relationship.

Conclusion

To summarize, it is evident that effective communication skills play a vital role in improving marital satisfaction. Moreover, it is important to highlight that the influence of communication skills on marital satisfaction is heightened by perfectionism. According to the results of this study, it is advised that couples

concentrate on fostering and improving the aspects that support communication skills. Furthermore, more attention should be given to perfectionism.

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